

POST-HARVEST LOSSES AND BUSINESS SUSTAINABILITY AT F&V MARKETS: A CASE STUDY OF MUZAFFARGARH

Choudary Ihtasham Ali^{*1}, Zainab Khan², Hafiz Bilal Ahmed Sabri³, Farrukh Shahzad⁴,
Khadija Syed⁵, Muhammad Najeeb Faiz⁶, Mohsin Raza⁷

^{*1,6}Directorate of Agriculture (Economics & Marketing) – Punjab (District; Muzaffargarh), Food Safety and
Consumer Protection Department, Govt. of Punjab, Pakistan

^{2,3,4,5,7}Department of Agricultural and Resource Economics, MNS University of Agriculture, Multan.

¹c.ihtasham@yahoo.com, ²zainab401240@gmail.com, ³saabri45@gmail.com,
⁴farrukh210383@gmail.com, ⁵ksyed00003@gmail.com, ⁶eada.muzaffargarh@yahoo.com,
⁷mohsinji774@gmail.com

Corresponding Author: *

Choudary Ihtasham Ali

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18181447>

Received	Accepted	Published
20 October 2025	16 December 2025	31 December 2025

ABSTRACT

Postharvest losses across the food and supply chain are one of the major concerns for achieving food security and economic sustainability in developing countries, like Pakistan. The market intermediaries, i.e., dealers and commission agents, play a central role throughout the food supply chain in Pakistan, from farm production to the end consumer. This study investigates the volume and causes of food losses, and post-harvest management by these market intermediaries at Fruit & Vegetable (F&V) markets in district Muzaffargarh, one of the major producers of essential commodities in the South Punjab region of Pakistan. A survey was conducted in four (04) F&V markets of the district to collect data on a pre-tested questionnaire, through simple random sampling, from 94 F&V market intermediaries. The descriptive statistics and econometric models, including multiple linear and binary logistic regressions, were employed for data analysis. The result reveals that every market intermediary experiences an average of 100-200 kg per day, valued at about 1,500 to 3,000 rupees per day, majorly due to rotten and damaged produce (85%). The finding highlights that the causes of food losses in the F&V markets reported by market intermediaries include storage facilities (77.7%), inadequate handling (69.9%), and inadequate packaging (61.7%). The result of the multiple linear regression indicates that the lack of storage facilities and inadequate packaging significantly increase food waste, whereas the intermediaries' training and their business experience reduce the food waste at the market level. Furthermore, result describes that business sustainability is positively associated with access to training, advisory services, and credit facilities for the market intermediaries. The study concludes that post-harvest losses are a substantial economic drain, driven by infrastructural deficits and market inefficiencies. It is recommended that the targeted interventions, including investment in cold storage infrastructure, training programs on post-harvest handling, and improved market mechanisms, must be adopted to enhance the resilience and profitability of F&V market intermediaries in the region.

Keywords: Post-harvest losses, food waste, fruit and vegetable markets, business sustainability

INTRODUCTION

The country Pakistan is one of the agro-based economies in the world, with the agriculture sector contributing about 23.5% to the national GDP

and providing employment to about 37% labour force of the country (GOP, 2025). Within the agriculture sector, the sub-sector horticulture has

emerged as a main sub-sector for ensuring domestic food security, in addition to a significant source of foreign exchange earnings via fruits and vegetables exports (Khan et al., 2024; Van den Broeck and Maertens, 2016). The diversified climatic conditions of the region encourage the production of a wide range of fruits, i.e., mangoes, dates, Phalsa, and vegetables, i.e., potatoes, tomatoes, onions, and chilies (Chandio et al., 2024; Shah et al., 2022).

Despite this diversified potential, the potential of horticultural glut is severely affected by one of the major persistent problems: post-harvest losses. According to some estimates in Pakistan, about 15-40% of every fruit and vegetable production is lost from harvest to consumption (Firdous, 2021; Ghafoor et al., 2022; Khan et al., 2025). These losses represent a multi-dimensional crisis. These losses reduce the income of farmers and market intermediaries, diminish export potential, and raise the prices for consumers (Khan et al., 2025; Nitikaroon and Petrat, 2024). Moreover, from a social perspective, these losses intensify food insecurity and poverty among those rural communities that rely on agriculture (Shahbazi et al., 2025).

The district Muzaffargarh in the South Punjab region is a significant contributor to Punjab's agricultural output, particularly known for its production of essential fruits and vegetables, including, i.e., mangoes, dates, citrus, and various vegetables (SMEDA, 2021). Like the other regions of Pakistan, in Muzaffargarh, the supply chain of these perishable fruits and vegetables is mainly characterized by many small-scale market intermediaries, i.e., dealers, brokers, commission agents, and pharia, who work in F&V markets usually without any up-to-date infrastructure and training (Asad & Gondal, 2022; UAF, 2022). These market intermediaries serve as the central link in connecting many scattered smallholder farmers with consumers, retailers, and other distribution networks. But they still work in this challenging environment (UAF, 2022).

Existing literature on post-harvest food losses in Pakistan, especially in Punjab, is limited, and most of those studies focus on losses at the farm level, household level, and during shipping only. The literature highlighted problems like poor harvesting and handling techniques, insufficient facilities for on-farm storage, and inefficient and inadequate transportation infrastructure (Ahmad

et al., 2021; Ahmed et al., 2015; Chandio et al., 2024; Firdous, 2021; Ghafoor et al., 2022; Khan et al., 2025; Naseer et al., 2024; Rahman et al., 2023; Shahbazi et al., 2025). However, there are relatively few targeted studies on the post-harvest food losses in F&V markets of Punjab, especially in the region of South Punjab, Pakistan. So, the area for research on post-harvest food losses at F&V markets in the South Punjab region and difficulties experienced by F&V market intermediaries still need to be explored. Furthermore, in addition to reducing the losses in markets, the market intermediaries also face unique pressures, including the need for rapid turnover, exposure to price fluctuations, and the burden of handling large volumes of highly perishable commodities without adequate facilities at the market level in the region (Firdous, 2021; Khan et al., 2025).

The post-harvest food losses at F&V markets are not just a transfer of on-farm losses to the market; the market environment and operations often create and intensify food losses at the marketing stage of the supply chain (Ghafoor et al., 2022). Limiting factors, such as a lack of storage facilities, force market intermediaries to sell their product at lower rates due to the perishability of fruits and vegetables (Faiz et al., 2020; Gunarathna and Mahinda Bandara, 2020; Ül Kirci et al., 2022). Inadequate packaging of produce triggers mechanical damage during handling, storage, and transportation of food (Farhan et al., 2010). Furthermore, as sorting and grading are not typically followed by local farmers, this causes the deterioration of high-quality produce to occur more quickly, as it may be packed alongside damaged or rotten produce. Including these management practices, a hidden factor, price volatility, makes it unviable to handle perishable commodities, resulting in intended wastage / postharvest losses at the market level (Naseer, 2024).

Accordingly, there is a need to identify the volume and causes of post-harvest losses at the market level to address these challenges. It is also compulsory to design effective measures to tackle these challenges, as policymakers and other government institutions need targeted and evidence-based findings to address these challenges of the F&V market intermediaries. So, the objective of this research is to bridge this gap by investigating the F&V market intermediaries of the district Muzaffargarh.

The objectives of this study are (1) to profile the socio-demographic and business characteristics of fruit and vegetable dealers in Muzaffargarh; (2) to quantify the extent and monetary value of post-harvest food losses at the market level; (3) to assess the primary types and causes of these food losses; (4) to identify their waste management practices; and (5) to investigate the factors that influence the level of losses and the sustainability of their businesses. Therefore, this research presents a detailed analysis of the problems in this sector of the supply chain and provides practical solutions to reduce losses, improve dealer profits, and enhance the overall efficiency of the South Punjab horticulture industry.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was conducted in the F&V markets of the District Muzaffargarh, one of the renowned districts in agricultural production across the South Punjab region, Pakistan (SMEDA, 2021). This study area was selected for research due to its potential for producing essential commodities, vegetables, and fruits in the region (SMEDA, 2021). The research considered the active and registered F&V market intermediaries, i.e., dealers, to ensure a true representation of stakeholders directly engaged in post-harvest handling and marketing activities at the market level. By considering this, real-time and authentic information was collected to investigate the research objectives.

For the survey, a pre-tested and well-structured web-based questionnaire was employed to collect the data from F&V market intermediaries. The web-based tool named KoboCollect was used in questionnaire development and data collection, and a simple random sampling technique was employed for the survey. The total number of respondents was 94, from whom the data was collected about socio-demographic information, business operations, assessment of post-harvest losses, waste management strategies, access to training and advisory services, and perceived operational challenges.

For data analysis, descriptive statistics, and econometric models, including multiple linear and binary logistic regression, were employed using SPSS software. Descriptive statistics include the calculation of the frequencies, percentages, means, and ranges to review the main characteristics of the

market intermediaries. Multiple linear regression was employed to estimate the factors affecting the post-harvest losses at the market level experienced by the market intermediaries at F&V markets. Various factors, including age, education, experience, business volume, and lack of storage facilities, inadequate packaging, price volatility, access to training and advisory services, were considered in multiple linear regression.

Multiple Linear Regression (Determinants of Post-Harvest Food Losses)

Food Waste

$$= \beta_0 + \beta_1(\text{Age}) + \beta_2(\text{Education}) + \beta_3(\text{Experience}) + \beta_4(\text{Business Volume}) + \beta_5(\text{Lack of Storage}) + \beta_6(\text{Inadequate Packaging}) + \beta_7(\text{Price Volatility}) + \beta_8(\text{Training}) + \beta_9(\text{Advisory Services}) + \varepsilon$$

Where β_0 is the intercept, β_1 ... β_9 are the coefficients of the independent variables, and ε is the error term.

To explore the factors for business sustainability at F&V markets, a binary logistic regression was employed as follows.

Binary Logistic Regression (Business Sustainability)

$$\text{Logit}(P) = \beta_0 + \beta_1(\text{Training}) + \beta_2(\text{Advisory}) + \beta_3(\text{Credit Access}) + \beta_4(\text{Business Volume}) + \beta_5(\text{Price Volatility}) + \beta_6(\text{Market Committee Support}) + \varepsilon$$

Where P is the probability that the business is sustainable. β_0 is the intercept, β_1 ... β_6 are the coefficients of the independent variables, and ε is the error term.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The findings of the study highlighted that market intermediaries in the F&V markets of District Muzaffargarh are mainly middle-aged (31-40 years), with a mean age of 38 years, and only about 14% are above 50. The young ones (aged from 20 to 30 years) also represent about one fourth of the intermediary population, that are about 26% in our study sample, which is very good for a food dealer to spend a longer span of his in the business. The results are represented in the following Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age (Years)		
20-30	25	26.6
31-40	34	36.2
41-50	22	23.4
51 and above	13	13.8
Education (Years)		
5-8	30	31.9
9-12	40	42.6
Above 12	24	25.5
Experience (Years)		
0-5	20	21.3
6-10	48	51.1
Above 10	26	27.6

The descriptive statistic further describes that most market intermediaries (42.6%) had 9-12 years of schooling, representing the existence of a moderate level of literacy in the study area, and 25.5% of intermediaries had completed their education above 12 years, which collectively make 68.1% of intermediaries having a sound education level. It has been observed in the literature that a moderate level of education is considered a positive asset for the adoption of new knowledge and practices related to better post-harvest management (Bisheko & G, 2023). Furthermore, about 51% of intermediaries had about 6-10 years of experience in the F&V business in the market, and about

27.6% had more than 10 years of experience, which is a considerable resource for addressing the difficulty of the F&V business in the market (Aziz et al., 2025).

The business volume at any market indicates the economic activity and operational scale of the market intermediaries, which have a direct influence on supply chain efficiency, price fluctuation, and post-harvest losses management. Figure 1 represents the daily business volume of F&V market intermediaries.

Figure 1: Daily Business Volume of F&V Market Intermediaries in Tons

The statistic represents that the market intermediaries of the study area are primarily medium-scale business entities. 40% of the

intermediaries had 5-10 tons of daily business volume, 28% had 10-15 tons of daily business volume, only 13% had above 15 tons of daily

business volume, and 19% of intermediaries had less than 5 tons of daily business volume. This daily business volume indicates the efficiency of

intermediaries as a matter of economic importance.

Figure 2: Distribution of Monthly Income of Intermediaries (PKR)

The statistic indicates that about 38% of the intermediaries earned between PKR 40,001-80,000, and about 31% earned between PKR 80,001-120,000 in a month. Only 14% of the intermediaries earned above 120,000 PKR monthly. This statistic indicates that most of the intermediaries earned a modest income in a month, which further describes the livelihood standard of intermediaries and their families. Moving on from the socio-economic statistics, the intermediaries of F&V markets were also asked to

report the type of food waste. The intermediaries identified several types of waste, which are represented in Figure 3. Rotten produce was the most prevalent (85.1%), followed by damaged produce (74.5%), overripe fruits/vegetables (59.6%), and packaging waste (55.3%). The high occurrence of rotting and damaged waste directly highlighted the lack of handling and storage facilities across the supply chain (Khan et al., 2025; Manzoor et al., 2021).

Figure 3: Types of Waste identified by F&V Dealers

After the volume of waste has been quantified, it has come to light that intermediaries reported about 100-200 Kg (0.1-0.2 Tons) of waste (including food and non-food waste) on an average

daily basis. On valuing the reported waste, just food waste costs about 1,000-3,000 PKR loss to intermediaries daily, which represents a significant economic loss of edible food daily at the market level.

As the surveyed F&V market intermediaries are earning a median range income in a month, this daily economic loss directly impacts their earnings and reduces their profits, increasing the financial burden on them to either further invest in the business or to support their families efficiently. This estimate is consistent with economic losses due to the post-harvest losses reported at the national level in the Pakistan horticulture sector (Ghafoor et al., 2022; Khan et al., 2025).

As it was observed earlier that intermediaries are facing a significant amount of food losses in terms of wastage, also facing financial loss in terms of economic value of waste, so here, it is also compulsory to identify the root causes of these losses borne by intermediaries at F&V markets. For this, about 77.7% of market intermediaries reported that the lack of storage facilities is one of the major causes for such significant food losses at the survey markets. They have to place the perishable produce in open platforms to sell due to a lack of proper storage facilities, which are exposed to extreme weather conditions, causing spoilage (Ahmad et al., 2021). This result is further supported by the econometric analysis (Table 2), where the lack of storage facilities showed a highly significant positive association ($B=5.85$, $p<0.001$) with food waste, describing it as one of the major factors for food waste losses at the market.

Figure 4: Major Causes of Food Waste at F&V Markets

Secondly, the most significant major reported cause of food waste at the market is inadequate handling, which is reported by about 64.9% of intermediaries. After that, inadequate packaging was reported by about 61.7% of market intermediaries, which is also a root cause of injury and rotting of produce during the whole supply

chain. Econometric analysis also demonstrates the significantly positive impact of inadequate packaging on food waste losses ($B=4.20$, $p<0.001$). Transportation issues were also reported by about 51.1% of respondents, which may cause delays for the delivery of produce, further intensifying the food waste losses (Ahmad et al., 2021; UAF, 2022).

Table 2: Factors Contributing towards Food Waste Generation

Variable	Coefficient (B)	Std. Error	t-Value
Constant	15.25***	4.37	3.49
Age (Years)	-0.10**	0.05	-2.00
Education (Years)	-0.25**	0.12	-2.08
Experience (Years)	-0.30***	0.08	-3.75
Business Volume (Tons/Day)	1.50***	0.40	3.75

Lack of Storage	5.85***	1.25	4.68
Inadequate Packaging	4.20***	1.10	3.82
Price Volatility	3.10**	1.20	2.58
Training Received	-6.30***	1.50	-4.20
Advisory Services	-2.70**	1.20	-2.25
R-squared	0.58		
F-statistic	23.40***		

The results of the Multiple Linear Regression model for food waste (kg/day) were statistically significant (F-statistic=23.40, $p<0.001$) and explained 58% of the variance in losses (R-squared=0.58), and are presented in Table 2, describing the factors contributing to the food waste generation at F&V markets.

The result of multiple linear regression quantified the factors contributing to food waste generation at the surveyed F&V markets. The socioeconomic factors of intermediaries, including age, education, and experience significantly negatively associated with food waste generation in the market. The result indicates that as the age increases by one-year, daily waste generation decreases by an average of 0.10 kg (B = -0.10, $p=0.048$), similarly as the education increases by a year, the waste generation decreases by an average of 0.25 Kg (B = -0.25, $p=0.040$), and each additional year of experience led to a more significant decrease of food waste by an average of 0.30 kg per day (B = -0.30, $p<0.001$). Whereas this amount of waste reduction is very small on an individual basis, if the intermediary is older, more experienced, and well educated, he will be able to manage the waste more efficiently and effectively, based on his knowledge, market tactics, and management skills gained over time in unpredictable market conditions (Iqbal et al., 2022; Nawaz et al., 2021).

Furthermore, considering the business factors, the result indicates that an additional ton of business

volume creates an additional 1.5 kg of waste daily (B = 1.50, $p<0.001$), intermediaries with a lack of storage facilities produce 5.85 kg of waste daily more than those who have access to storage facilities (B = 5.85, $p<0.001$), and similarly inadequate packaging, and price volatility increases the food waste generation by 4.20 kg and 3.10 kg daily, respectively (B = 4.20, $p<0.001$; B = 3.10, $p=0.011$). These statistics endorsed that these infrastructural and market deficiencies are the key factors contributing to the food waste generation/post-harvest losses at the F&V markets level (Ahmad et al., 2021; Firdous, 2021; Ghafoor et al., 2022; Khan et al., 2025; Naseer et al., 2024; Nitikaroon and Petrat, 2024; UAF, 2022).

In addition to socioeconomic, structural, and market factors, the influence of extension services by the public departments was also analysed. Most significantly, access to formal training emerged as the single most effective tool for reducing waste (Mbesa et al., 2024). Intermediaries who had received any training on food waste management wasted an average of 6.30 kg less per day than those who had no training at all (B = -6.30, $p<0.001$). Moreover, the access to advisory services also showed a negative impact, resulting in a reduction of 2.70 kg of daily waste (B = -2.70, $p=0.027$), though its effect was less than the access to the formal training on waste management.

Table 3: Factors affecting Business Sustainability

Variable	Coefficient (B)	Std. Error	z-Value
Constant	-0.85**	0.35	-2.43
Training	1.35***	0.40	3.38
Advisory Services	0.95***	0.30	3.17
Credit Access	0.85***	0.28	3.04
Business Volume (Tons/Day)	0.20**	0.10	2.00
Price Volatility	-0.72**	0.35	-2.06
Market Committee Support	0.50*	0.29	1.72
R-Squared	0.518		
F-Statistics	21.34**		

For estimating the factors affecting the business sustainability at the F&V market, a binary logistic regression was employed, and the results are presented in Table 3. The results revealed that access to training ($B = 1.35, p=0.001$), advisory services ($B = 0.95, p=0.002$), and credit facilities ($B = 0.85, p=0.002$) significantly enhanced the business sustainability by 1.35, 0.95, and 0.85 log odds, respectively. These statistics indicate that knowledge and financial resources are the main

factors for business sustainability at surveyed F&V markets.

Moreover, the result indicates that an additional ton of daily business volume increases the business sustainability by 0.20 units ($B = 0.20, p=0.046$), highlighting the advantages of economies of scale. On the other hand, price volatility showed destabilized effects on business sustainability ($B = -0.72, p=0.039$), which directly threatens the long-term sustainability of market intermediaries in the F&V market.

Figure 3: Food Waste Management Practices at F&V Markets

The study also figured out the waste management methods being commonly practiced by the F&V market intermediaries. It is observed that mostly intermediaries practice very common and environmentally unsustainable methods for waste management. The result shows that the most used and top methods were throwing the waste in open bins/yards, practiced by about 45% of intermediaries, which indicates a serious concern for public health and environmental pollution. About 30% of intermediaries feed their food waste to animals, which is a somewhat beneficial method. Only 15% of intermediaries reported that they compost their food waste, which represents a sustainable and eco-friendly waste management practice, but is adopted by a very limited number of market intermediaries. The described lack of organized waste management and recycling systems highlights an urgent need for policy and entrepreneurial attention (Rashid et al., 2025; Siddiqua et al., 2022).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The study described the main and persistent challenges faced by fruit and vegetable (F&V) market intermediaries in District Muzaffargarh, South Punjab, highlighting the analytical condition of food waste/post-harvest losses at the market level. The scale of post-harvest losses is significant, as an individual intermediary loses about 100-200 kg of produce daily. These losses are not just a statistic but a significant economic loss, driven by deeply rooted structural deficiencies. The primary causes identified by the intermediaries include a lack of cold storage facilities, high volatility in market prices, which makes difficulties in planning and sales difficult, and the common use of inadequate packaging materials and methods.

Furthermore, the study also found a significant and negative influence of formal training on food waste generation, describing that knowledge and skills serve as remedial measures for post-harvest losses at the market. However, the statistic that only about

40% of intermediaries have access to formal training about waste management, which reveals the current significant gap in extension support services, further describes the need for potential improvements in extension support.

Subsequently, the study stated deliverable recommendations for intervention. Although infrastructural and market deficiencies are significant, the analysis confirms that intermediaries equipped with training in post-harvest management methods prove capable of significantly reducing their post-harvest losses. This suggests that sustainability within this sector is an achievable goal, one that can be systematically fostered through a synergistic approach combining knowledge transfer via training, financial inclusion through improved credit access, and strategic operational scaling. Therefore, effective policy must be multi-pronged. It should advocate for public-private partnerships to develop critical cold storage chains and modern warehousing facilities. Furthermore, agricultural extension services must be renewed to deliver regular, targeted training on proper handling, grading, and packaging. Concurrently, market reforms, such as enhanced price information systems, should be explored to mitigate price volatility. Ultimately, promoting sustainable waste management practices, such as composting, could transform a current environmental liability into a new economic opportunity. By strategically addressing these interconnected areas, stakeholders can collectively work to curtail post-harvest losses, sustain intermediaries' incomes, enhance food security, and fortify the horticultural value chain throughout Pakistan.

REFERENCES

- Ahmad, K., Afridi, M., Khan, N. A., & Sarwar, A. (2021). Quality Deterioration of Postharvest Fruits and Vegetables in Developing Country Pakistan: A Mini Overview. *Asian Journal of Agriculture and Food Sciences*, 9(2), 83–90. <https://doi.org/10.24203/ajafs.v9i2.6615>
- Ahmed, U. I., Ying, L., Mushtaq, K., & Khalid Bashir, M. (2015). an Econometric Estimation of Post Harvest Losses of Kinnow in Pakistan. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management United Kingdom*, III(5), 773–783. <http://ijecm.co.uk/>
- Asad, S. A., & Gondal, O. H. (2022). *Role of Supply Chains in Determining Farmers' Productivity and Consumer Prices*. LUMS. <https://mhrc.lums.edu.pk/role-of-supply-chains-in-determining-farmers-productivity-and-consumer-prices>
- Aziz, R. Al, Arman, M. H., Karmaker, C. L., Morshed, S. M., Bari, A. B. M. M., & Islam, A. R. M. T. (2025). Exploring the challenges to cope with ripple effects in the perishable food supply chain considering recent disruptions: Implications for urban supply chain resilience. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 11(1), 100449. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joitmc.2024.100449>
- Bisheko, M. J., & G, R. (2023). Major barriers to adoption of improved postharvest technologies among smallholder farmers in sub-Saharan Africa and South Asia: A systematic literature review. *World Development Sustainability*, 2(June 2022), 100070. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wds.2023.10000>
- Chandio, A. A., Gokmenoglu, K. K., Joyo, M. A., & Jiang, Y. (2024). Modeling the climate change impacts on major fruits production: Recent evidence from Pakistan. *Scientia Horticulturae*, 324(112618). <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scienta.2023.112618>
- Faiz, M. R., Ashraf, I., Nawaz, H., Zubair, M., Mahmood, M. S., Hussain, S., & Qadeer, A. (2020). Identification and Prioritization of Issues in Growing and Marketing Vegetables in Punjab Province of Pakistan. *Journal of Innovative Sciences*, 6(1), 2–7. <https://doi.org/10.17582/journal.jis/2020/6.1.54.59>
- Farhan, A., Saeed, H., & Khan, S. N. (2010). Post harvest losses of tomato in markets of district Lahore. *Mycopath*, 8(2), 97–99. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/274254283_Post_harvest_losses_of_tomato_in_markets_of_district_Lahore

- Firdous, N. (2021). Post-harvest losses in different fresh produces and vegetables in Pakistan with particular focus on tomatoes. *Journal of Horticulture and Postharvest Research*, 4(1), 71–86.
<https://doi.org/10.22077/jhpr.2020.3168.1125>
- Ghafoor, A., Basher, M. A., Badar, H., & Lee, S. (2022). *Building horticulture value chains and reducing postharvest losses in Pakistan* (No. 235; ADB Briefs).
<http://dx.doi.org/10.22617/brf220545-2>
- GOP, G. of P. (2025). *PAKISTAN ECONOMIC SURVEY 2024-25*.
https://www.finance.gov.pk/survey/chapter_25/2_Agriculture.pdf
- Gunarathna, R. T., & Mahinda Bandara, Y. (2020). Post Harvest Losses and the Role of Intermediaries in the Vegetable Supply Chain. *MERCon 2020 - 6th International Multidisciplinary Moratuwa Engineering Research Conference, July 2020*, 378–383.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/MERCon50084.2020.9185197>
- Iqbal, A., Abdullah, Y., Nizami, A. S., Sultan, I. A., & Sharif, F. (2022). Assessment of Solid Waste Management System in Pakistan and Sustainable Model from Environmental and Economic Perspective. *Sustainability*, 14(19).
<https://doi.org/10.3390/su141912680>
- Khan, S., Shah, A., & Ijaz, N. (2025). Identification of Root Causes of Post-harvest Food Losses in the Mango Supply Chain: A Case of Sindh and Punjab, Pakistan. *Human Nature Journal of Social Sciences*, 6(2), 235–253.
<https://doi.org/10.71016/hnjss/x51w2w80>
- Khan, U. E., Ejaz, H., & Atiq, F. (2024). *Evaluation of Pakistan's Horticulture Export Potential-An Application of the Gravity Model*.
- Manzoor, A., Ahmad Maan, A., Ahmad Khan, I., & Shahbaz, B. (2021). a Mixed-Method Study To Enhance Food Security By Reducing Post-Harvest Wheat Losses in Punjab, Pakistan. *Humanities & Social Sciences Reviews*, 9(2), 87–99.
<https://doi.org/10.18510/hssr.2021.929>
- Mbesa, B., Makindara, J., Kadigi, M., Majubwa, R., & Madege, R. (2024). Effect of Training on Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice on the Use of Hermetic Storage Technologies among Smallholder Farmers in Tanzania. *African Journal of Empirical Research*, 5(2), 881–893.
<https://doi.org/10.51867/ajernet.5.2.79>
- Naseer, M. A. ur R. (2024). *Decoding the Dynamics of Pricing in the Fruit and Vegetable Market: Highlighting the Government Imperfections*.
<https://pide.org.pk/research/decoding-the-dynamics-of-pricing-in-the-fruit-and-vegetable-market-highlighting-the-government-imperfections/>
- Naseer, M. A. ur R., Ayyaz, S., Asim, M., Akhtar, S., Iqbal, M. A., Afzal, M. F., & Ahmad, A. (2024). Analysis of Domestic Goods Transport and Logistics Dynamics within the Agricultural Supply Chain in Pakistan. *Journal of Economic Impact*, 6(3), 304–311.
<https://doi.org/10.52223/econimpact.2024.6316>
- Nawaz, M., Yousafzai, M. T., Khan, S., Ahmad, W., Salman, M., Han, H., Ariza-Montes, A., & Vega-Muñoz, A. (2021). Assessing the formal and informal waste recycling business processes through a stakeholders lens in Pakistan. *Sustainability*, 13(21), 1–16.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/su132111717>
- Nitikaroon, K., & Petrat, K. (2024). Economic evaluation of post-harvest vegetable losses. *International Journal of Financial Management and Economics*, 7(1), 98–100.
<https://doi.org/10.33545/26179210.2024.v7.i1.265>
- Rahman, K. U., Hussain, A., Ejaz, N., Shang, S., Balkhair, K. S., Khan, K. U. J., Khan, M. A., & Rehman, N. U. (2023). Analysis of production and economic losses of cash crops under variable drought: A case study from Punjab province of Pakistan. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 85(103507).
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdr.2022.103507>

- Rashid, S., Sultan, H., Rashid, W., Talpur, B. D., Tulcan, R. X. S., Khan, M. T., Bohnett, E., Korai, M. S., & Zhang, L. (2025). A critical review of opportunities and challenges of solid waste management in an emerging economy- evidence from Pakistan. *Environmental Development*, 55(101182). <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envdev.2025.101182>
- Shah, M. H., Rafique, R., Almas, M., Usman, M., Yasin, S., & Bibi, S. (2022). A Review: Fruit Production Industry of Pakistan Trends, Issues and Way Forward. *Pakistan Journal of Agricultural Research*, 35(3). <https://doi.org/10.17582/journal.pjar/2022/35.3.523.532>
- Shahbazi, F., Shahbazi, S., & Zare, D. (2025). Losses in Agricultural Produce: Causes and Effects on Food Security. *Food and Energy Security*, 14(3). <https://doi.org/10.1002/fes3.70086>
- Siddiqua, A., Hahladakis, J. N., & Al-Attia, W. A. K. A. (2022). An overview of the environmental pollution and health effects associated with waste landfilling and open dumping. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 29(39), 58514–58536. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-022-21578-z>
- SMEDA. (2021). *Dates Cluster*, Muzaffargarh. https://smeda.org/phocadownload/Punjab/cluster_profiles/dates_cluster_muzaffargarh.pdf
- UAF, U. of A. F. (2022). *Regional: Agricultural Value Chain Development in Selected Asian Countries* (Issue June).
- Ül Kirci, M., Isaksson, O., & Seifert, R. (2022). Managing Perishability in the Fruit and Vegetable Supply Chains. *Sustainability*, 14(9). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14095378>
- Van den Broeck, G., & Maertens, M. (2016). Horticultural exports and food security in developing countries. *Global Food Security*, 10(October), 11–20. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gfs.2016.07.007>